

Structural design methods of component based lattice composites for the Elytra Pavilion

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Abstract

The focus of this paper is on the structural engineering design approach for coreless filament wound composite lattices. This approach has been in active development since the first ICD/ITKE Research Pavilion in 2012. The current approach, described in this paper has been recently tested and validated during the design of the Elytra Filament Pavilion, a 200 m² canopy roof consisting of structural carbon and glass fibre reinforced polymers developed and built by an interdisciplinary collaboration at the University of Stuttgart.

Keywords: Carbon & Glass Fibre Composites, FRP Fibre reinforced Polymers, Structural Design, Modelling and Simulation, Lightweight Structures, Innovative Structural Systems

Figure 1: The 9 kg/m² structural weight of the Elytra Pavilion show the lightweight potential of lattice composites, Vitra Campus, Weil am Rhein, Germany © Julien Lanoo

1 Introduction

High strength to weight ratio, corrosion resistance and a tensile strength in a range of 2-4 GPa make technical composite materials interesting for lightweight constructions. E.g. more than 50% of a modern aircraft consist of these materials, see Airbus Innovative Materials [1].

However, the majority of structures in the building industry are made of steel, concrete, masonry, timber and glass. There is very little usage of structural composites in today's building sector. There are many reasons for this but a significant one is the lack of knowledge amongst designers about how to best fabricate and utilise these specialist, customisable materials.

The Aerospace industry – where work on composite lattice structures is under development since the 1980s – shows that the direct substitution of aluminium with composite sheets will save 10-20% mass. While a designed composite lattice grid can achieve a 40 to 60% saving (Vasiliev V.V., 2006 [12]). These developments are only now finding any relevance within construction and architecture as relevant fabrication processes are developed.

The authors work is on the engineering design methods for the structural application of lattice composites in architecture. Knippers J. and Menges A. *Fibres Rethought – Towards Novel Constructional Articulation* [3], Knippers, J.; Koslowski, V.; Solly, J.; Fildhuth, T. *Modular Coreless Filament Winding for Lightweight Systems in Architecture* [4], Parascho S., Knippers J., Dörstelmann M., Prado M., Menges A. *Modular Fibrous Morphologies: Computational Design, Simulation and Fabrication of Differentiated Fibre Composite Building Components* [4].

2 Composite engineering design concepts

Composites are used in a broad range of industries for decades. Also in the building industry. However, the coreless filament winding – that is used to fabricate the lattice composite of the Elytra Pavilion – is a novel method of processing fibre reinforcement and matrix to a structural member. The technical differences of these lattice grids to the well-established processing methods for composites are highlighted in this chapter to present the thereof resulting design strategies for lattice composites.

2.1 Typical composite layup versus lattice composites

Typical structural composites consist of multiple textiles that are stacked on top of each other. A textile is either a woven or a non-woven planar sheet made of carbon or glass filaments. A variety of woven textiles with different drape-ability properties allows to place planar reinforcement sheets on almost arbitrarily double curved moulds without wrinkles. For high performance application non-woven textiles are preferred as the undulation of a fibre strand – resulting from the weaving process – leads to a reduction of the fibre strength. The textiles are impregnated with a matrix before or after the placement on a mould. Matrix materials are usually thermoplastic or thermoset polymers like epoxy or unsaturated polyester resin.

Figure 2: Typical composite layup consisting of multiple sheets with fibre reinforcement
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Figure 3: Lattice composite with differentiated fibre orientations consisting of parallel fibre bundles
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The Classical Laminate Theory (CLT) is the state of the art method for the analytical determination of the mechanical properties of the fibre composites. It considers a laminate as a continuous stack of individual, homogeneous fibre mats.

2.2 Lattice composite modelling and design concepts

The Elytra Pavilion's lattice laminate does not fulfil the prerequisites of the CLT. Modelling all fibre bundles of the lattice with beam elements is technically possible but has the following disadvantages that make it not applicable for architectural structures:

- The lattice grid modelled with beam elements requires an accurate description of the cross section geometry of each composite strand. During the winding process fibres are pulled along of each other which leads to many changes of the cross sectional dimensions. Only an averaged cross section can be used for the simulation, this cause unavoidable inaccuracies and incorrect stiffnesses.
- The stiffness and strengths of the joints – formed by fibres that are placed on top of each other before the resin cures as part of the coreless filament winding process – depend on the consolidation, potential air that remained between the fibre bundles and the contact surface. These parameters vary vastly within the components due to non-constant fibre tension as well as resin volume content of the current fabrication setup. Hence the failure modes of the nodes can't currently be simulated with an appropriate precision.
- The location and orientation of the composite strands depends strongly on the fabrication. Due to its strong directionality a small error of 5 degrees results to a huge reduction of the stiffness and strength. Hence a well described geometry containing all fibre bundles locations and orientations of the manufactured lattice would be needed to model the composite.

Figure 4: Lattice composite and Finite-Element-Model where all parallel fibre bundles are modelled with beam elements. Unknown stiffness and strength at fibre intersections, local buckling and computationally intensive analysis procedures require alternative modelling approaches © ICD/ITKE University of Stuttgart

As solution to this the authors propose a three-step multi-scale material tests procedure:

1. Small test coupons of the fibre bundle laminate are tested. The results are used for the preliminary sizing of the components.
2. The stiffness of the manufactured lattice composite component is determined experimentally and non-destructive. This measured stiffness is used for the simulation of the entire global structure to determine the joint forces, displacements, support forces, etc.
3. The decisive actions resulting from the simulation are applied to the lattice composite component to validate its load bearing capacity.

This approach considers imperfections resulting from resin impregnation, deformed winding frames, fibre layup etc.

3 Case study roof Elytra pavilion

The Elytra Pavilion is based on a the double layered shell structure that resulted from precedent biomimetic investigations on the morphology of the Elytra – the wing cover – of multiple beetles. This research lead to the ICD/ITKE Research Pavilion 2013-14 [4] Parascho S., Knippers J., Dörstelmann M., Prado M., Menges A. *Modular Fibrous Morphologies: Computational Design, Simulation and Fabrication of Differentiated Fibre Composite Building Components*.

The structural weight of the composite averages on 9 kg/m², the entire weight of the pavilion equals to 2.5 t. The covered area is 200 m².

The pavilion's roof is divided into 40 hexagonal components with a diameter of 2.4 m and a height of 0.4 m. The components are connected with 16 M6 bolts per edge. The roof is clad with transparent, non-structural polycarbonate sheets. Seven columns support the roof. Roof and the funnel shaped columns are coreless filament wound composites.

The used carbon fibre have a modulus of elasticity of 240 GPa and a characteristic strength of 4 GPa. The glass fibres modulus is 83 GPa, the characteristic strength 2.43 GPa. The modulus of the matrix equals to 3.05 GPa, the strength to 68 MPa and the elongation at break is between 7 and 10 %.

Figure 5: Left – the robot winds glass fibre bundles on a coreless steel frame that is removed after the resin has cured; Middle – the fibre placement tool of the robot winds a set of parallel filaments around a metal sleeve that is later used to join two components; Right – the contact between the fibres forms a lattice grid, double layered lattice grids are made by alternating the winding sequence © ICD/ITKE University of Stuttgart

The components are formed by winding the straight fibre strands on a hexagonal steel frame that is removed after the resin has cured, see Figure 5. The winding sequence determines the inner diameter or aperture of a component. With that it is possible to wind two lattice grids subsequently after each other on top of each other. These two lattice grids form a closed, tube like, cross section which follows along the hexagonal geometry of the winding frame.

The lower parts of the columns, the foundations and bolts and fasteners are made of steel. The structural steel of the columns is S355JR, the plates of the foundations are S235JR. All bolts and fasteners are grade 8.8 steel.

3.1 Load-bearing system of the lattice composite canopy

The roof of the Elytra Pavilion is a planar, segmented grillage that is inclined by 6 degrees. Each component of the grillage has a unique fibre layup and weight adapted to the loading it is subject to.

Dead, wind or snow loading on the grillage lead to bending in its components. The hexagonal outer shape and circular inner aperture of a component act structurally like a circular ring carrier with a hollow box profile. This structural typology transforms bending into torsion and ring forces, a very efficient load bearing mechanism.

The column heads are rigidly fixed to the grillage, its feet are pinned to the soil anchors to horizontally brace the canopy. The funnel shape of the columns follows the bending moment diagram. Within the

columns the funnel diameter downsizes from 2.4 m at the top to a 100 mm where it connects to the steel tube hollow section.

The thin lattice composite acts primarily membrane action, where the composite fibre bundles carry mainly tension and compression. Thus ensuring the lightweight nature of the components. Closed form prevents local thin-shell edge-buckling.

3.2 Structural design informed by mechanical component tests

The dimensioning and material placement strategy is to first place a shape defining glass fibre grid. This grid is reinforced with carbon fibres where they are structurally needed. The roof components vary their inner aperture, carbon fibre reinforcement and the edges and corners depending on the required strengths. The distribution of the various aperture sizes in the grillage was determined with a structural optimisation resulting in small, medium and largely reinforced components with unique corner reinforcements at the locations where loads are induced.

The glass fibre grid of the columns is strengthened with crossing carbon fibre beams. Its crossings and lengths are dimensioned by buckling calculations.

A series of multi-scale physical structural proof-of-concept models were investigated to validate the numerical simulations and to demonstrate the feasibility of the project as presented in section 2.2. The smallest unit that was examined was a single composite fibre bundle consisting of 50,000 carbon fibre filaments. With these results a detailed Finite-Element simulation was performed to predict the structural capacity. However, the global model of the entire structure required a coarser model with fewer degrees of freedom and shorter computation time that could be handled within the structural design process.

Figure 6: Determination of component stiffness considering fabrication and geometric imperfections
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Figure 7: Lattice composite modelled with shell elements, stiffness and weight adjusted to test data
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The fibre strand grid was therefore abstracted to a thin continuous surface with an averaged thickness, weight and experimentally determined stiffness. This process is necessary as within the hyperstatic grillage the stress resultants and joint forces depend on the stiffness of each component.

Figure 8: Finite-Element-Model of digitally assembled Elytra Pavilion with respect to factored wind uplift
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These calibrated components were digitally assembled to the global model. This technique allowed computation of the entire pavilions' structural capacity without a full-scale test of the built pavilion.

4 Conclusion and outlook

The Elytra Filament Pavilion case study demonstrates that the chosen multi-scale structural design approach is applicable within the requirements and boundary conditions of a building planning process. The average structural weight of 9 kg/m² shows the lightweight potential of coreless filament wound lattice components while considering standardised building code requirements.

As this is the first building of its kind, refinements and optimisation of the design process are to be developed alongside a proposal for a standardised engineering design code. A detailed method for the analysis of fibre grid structures that does not require component based tests is subject to undergoing developments. The mathematical prediction of the manufactured geometry of the coreless wound composite is investigated in a separate research project funded by the EU.

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